

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ
JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

ДАВРИЙЛИГИ: 2016-2025

ЖИЛД 10
СОҢ 2

2025

ЧОП
ЭТИЛГАН САНА:
30 АПРЕЛ, 2025 ЙИЛ

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

10 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 10, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 10, ISSUE 2

Бош муҳаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети Илмий ишлар ва инновациялар бўйича
проректори, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна
*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi
*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович
*тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Очилов Улугбек Усмонович
*PhD, доцент, СамДТУ Дипломдан кейинги таълим
факултети Психиатрия курси мудири. СамДТУ Илмий
кенгаши котиби. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Шавази Наргиз Нуралiena
*DSc. Доцент, СамДМУ 3-сон акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович
*Тоҷикистон Давлат тиббиёт университети Онкология
ва нур таъхиси кафедраси мудири, Тиббиёт фанлари
доктори, Профессор. Душанбе, Тоҷикистон.
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Сандов Сандамир Аброрович
*тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалжанов Ойбек Абдуҷаббарович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар
тери-таносил касалликлари ва ОИТС
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович
*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси профессори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич
*Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
2-сон Даволаш факултети декани,
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент.
Самарқанд, Ўзбекистон.*

Миржурев Элбек Миршавкатович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
ЎзССВ Тиббий ходимларни касбий малакасини
ривожлантириши марказининг Нейрореабилитация
кафедраси мудири, Тошкент, Ўзбекистон*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, проректор по научной работе и инновациям Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, профессор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, доцент кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического госпиталя Сеульского национального университета, Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, заведующий кафедрой Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины Ташкентской медицинской академии
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очилов Улугбек Усманович

PhD, доцент, заведующий курсом психиатрии факультета постдипломного образования СамГМУ. Секретарь Ученого совета СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc. доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Рашид Захидович

Заведующий кафедрой Онкологии и лучевой диагностики Таджикского медицинского университета, д.м.н., профессор, Душанбе, Таджикистан
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Саидов Сандамир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии, неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Даминов Феруз Асадуллаевич

Декан лечебного факультета №2 Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета, доктор медицинских наук, доцент. Самарканд, Узбекистан.

Мирджурев Эльбек Миршавкатович

Заведующий кафедрой Нейрореабилитации Центра развития профессиональной квалификации медицинских работников МЗ РУз, д.м.н., профессор Ташкент, Узбекистан

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Vice-Rector for scientific work
and Innovation, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shavkatovna
PhD, Docent Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine, Tashkent
Medical Academy. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich

*PhD, Docent, Head of the Psychiatry Course at the Faculty of
Postgraduate Education of SamSMU. Secretary of the Academic
Council of SamSMU. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Shavazi Nargiz Nuraliyena

*DSc, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Obstetrics
and Gynecology N 3 of Samarkand State Medical University.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Yuldashev Ravshan Zakhidovich

*Head of the Department of Oncology and Radiation Diagnostics
at Tajik State Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Dushanbe, Tajikistan <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Department of Dermatovenerology,
pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Daminov Feruz Asadullaevich

*Dean of the Faculty of Medicine No. 2, Samarkand State
Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate
Professor. Samarkand, Uzbekistan.*

Mirjuraev Elbek Mirshavkatovich

*Head of the Department of Neurorehabilitation Center
for the development of professional qualification of
medical workers, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Tashkent, Uzbekistan
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2111-4388>*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

MODERN APPROACHES IN PRACTICAL SURGERY

1.	Akhmedov Adkham Ibadullayeich, Fayazov Abdulaziz Djalilovich PREVENTION AND TREATMENT OF MOTOR-EVACUATION DYSFUNCTION OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT IN SEVERELY BURNED PATIENTS.....	11
2.	Arziev Ismoil Alievich TECHNIQUE AND FEATURES OF SURGICAL CORRECTION OF DAMAGE TO THE MAIN BILE DUCTS THAT OCCURRED INTRAOPERATIVELY.....	17
3.	Anarboev Sanjar Alisherovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF RECURRENT FORMS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....	26
4.	Askarova Nafisa Rinatovna VULVARICOSITY: FEATURES OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT IN PATIENTS WITH VARICOSE VEINS AND PREGNANT WOMEN.....	33
5.	Akhmedov Rakhmatillo Furkatovich SURGICAL TACTICS FOR IATROGENIC INJURIES TO THE BILE DUCTS.....	38
6.	Achilov Mirzakarim Temirovich SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PANCREATIC HEAD TUMORS.....	44
7.	Allazov Iskandar Salakh ogli CYSTIC KIDNEY NEOPLASMS: RETROSPECTIVE ASPECTS AND MODERN VIEWS.....	49
8.	Allazov Salakh Allazovich LAPAROSCOPIC AND RETROPERITONEOSCOPIC OPERATIONS IN UROLOGY...	57
9.	Bobokulov Nurullo Asadovich, Ablyatifov Aziz Baxriyarovich OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT IN UROLOGY: THE ROLE OF SIMULTANEOUS LAPAROSCOPIC OPERATIONS.....	66
10.	Bakhriddinov Bekzod Rustamovich, Aliev Mansur Abduholikovich MR SPECTROSCOPY OF BRAIN TUMORS AND CORRELATION OF METABOLIC CHANGES WITH HISTOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS.....	72
11.	Davronov Alisher Uktamovich, Kurbaniyazov Bobojon Zafarjonovich LAPAROSCOPIC REPAIR OF PERFORATED ULCERS: ADVANTAGES AND CLINICAL OUTCOMES.....	79
12.	Daminov Feruz Asatullaevich, Bobokulov Azamat Uktamovich FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF BLEEDING IN GASTRODUODENAL ULCERS. (LITERATURE REVIEW).....	88
13.	Davronov Oybek Otabek ugli MODERN VIEWS ON THE PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF CHANGES IN THE FORNICAL APPARATUS AND ADJACENT STRUCTURES DURING URINARY STONE DISEASE.....	95
14.	Egamberdiev Abdukakhkhor Abdukodirovich FEATURES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF HERNIA OF THE ESOPHAGEAL HOLE OF THE DIAPHRAGM.....	101
15.	Esirgapov Sardor Nursalimovich, Abduraxmanov Diyor Shukrullaevich RESULTS OF HERNIOPLASTY OF VENTRAL HERNIAS WITH ABDOMINOPTOSIS.....	106
16.	Gafarov Rushen Refatovich CLASSIFICATION OF POSTOPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS OF HOLMIUM LASER ENUCLEATION OF THE PROSTATE: ROLE OF A UNIFIED APPROACH.....	112
17.	Giyasova Nigora Kobilovna MODERN APPROACHES TO DETECTING ARTHROSIS AT EARLY STAGES AND POSSIBILITIES OF PATHOGENETIC TREATMENT OF THIS DISEASE.....	118

18.	Ishmuradov Bakhron Tursunovich EFFICACY OF ENDOSCOPIC BALLOON DILATION IN TREATMENT OF ACQUIRED URETERAL STRICTURES.....	127
19.	Islomov Nuriddin Komil ugli, Mustafakulov Ishnazar Boynazarovich, Julbekov Komil Islomovich MANAGEMENT FOR SIGMOID VOLVULUS.....	131
20.	Ismati Amir Olimovich, Mamarajabov Sobirjon Ergashevich, Anosov Viktor Davidovich A NOVEL PROGNOSTIC SYSTEM FOR 30-DAY MORTALITY IN PATIENTS WITH ULCER UPPER GASTROINTESTINAL BLEEDING.....	141
21.	Jalilov Khusan Mukhidinovich, Mansurov Jaloliddin Shamsiddinovich PREOPERATIVE INCIDENCE OF DEEP VEIN THROMBOSIS AFTER HIP FRACTURES IN KOREANS.....	151
22.	Kadirov Rustam Nadirovich, Khursanov Yokubjon Erkin ugli, Kamolov Sardor Jamolovich MODERN ASPECTS OF DIAGNOSING AND TREATMENT OF ACUTE PATHOLOGY OF THE ABDOMINAL CAVITY ORGANS.....	157
23.	Karabayev Djamshidkhan Shavkatovich, Shakhanov Shavkat Safarovich, Nekbayev Hasan Sayfulloyevich DETERMINATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS AND PREVENTION OF ARTHRITIS IN PATIENTS USING LOW-VIBRATION LASER BEAMS.....	162
24.	Kurbaniyazov Zafar Babajanovich, Mukhiddinov Bobur Khuroz Ugli, Askarov Pulat Azadovich EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY.....	168
25.	Khaidarov Numon Bozor ugli, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DESTRUCTIVE PANCREATITIS.....	175
26.	Khalimova Zamira Yusufovna, Narimova Gulchehra Jumaniyazovna, Kurbanova Sitara Shukhratovna, Ablakulova Munisa Xamrakulovna INTERACTION BETWEEN MELATONIN AND METABOLIC PARAMETERS IN OBESE WOMEN: A CLINICAL ANALYSIS.....	181
27.	Khurazov Ganisher Mususrmonovich MODERN APPROACHES TO TREATING PROSTACH ADENOMA: EFFICIENCY, SAFETY, AND IMPACT ON PATIENTS' LIFE QUALITY.....	190
28.	Khursanov Yokubjon Erkin ugli, Sattorov Abbos Xalilovich EFFICIENCY OF USING MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF COMPLICATED ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS.....	196
29.	Khamrakulov Shokhrukh Farukhovich, Mamarajabov Sobirzhon Irgashevich, Rasulov Khamidulla Abdullaevich LAPAROSCOPIC TREATMENT OF STRICTURED HERNIAS OF THE ANTERIOR ABDOMINAL WALL.....	201
30.	Khodjimatom Gulomidin Minkhodzhievich, Yigitov Ayubkhon Azizbekovich, Yahyoev Sardorbek Mamasobir ugli IMPROVING THE OUTCOMES OF TREATMENT OF COMBINED SURGICAL DISEASES OF ABDOMINAL ORGANS USING SIMULTANEOUS LAPAROSCOPIC SURGERIES.....	207
31.	Khaidarov Numon Bozor ugli, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH DESTRUCTIVE PANCREATITIS.....	217

32.	Khamdamov Olim Dilmurodovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich OPTIMIZATION OF TACTICAL AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PULMONARY ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....	223
33.	Khashimov Rustam Uktamjanovich, Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH INGUINAL HERNIAS.....	229
34.	Mamanov Muhammad Chorievich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TACTICS IN COMPLICATED AND COMPLEX FORMS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....	235
35.	Mamatov Karim Saidullaevich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich EFFECTIVENESS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS IN SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CHOLANGITIS.....	243
36.	Mardonov Bobosher Amirovich. SURGICAL TACTICS FOR POSTCHOLECYSTECTOMY SYNDROME: FEATURES AND CHALLENGES OF IMPLEMENTATION.....	249
37.	Mukhiddinov Temur Djakhangirovich, Askarov Pulat Azadovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF VENTRAL HERNIAS WITH CONCOMITANT PATHOLOGY OF ABDOMINAL ORGANS.....	256
38.	Mansurov Jalolidin Shamsidinovich COMPARISON OF ULTRASOUND-GUIDED HYDROSTATIC REDUCTION OF INTUSSUSCEPTION RESULTS BETWEEN PEDIATRIC AND NON-PEDIATRIC RADIOLOGISTS AND RESIDENTS.....	262
39.	Musoyev Sodikjon Toirovich MODERN ALGORITHMS FOR THE TREATMENT OF ACUTE AND CHRONIC CHOLECYSTITIS: FROM CONSERVATIVE THERAPY TO SURGERY.....	273
40.	Negmatov Ismatillo Savridinovich CT DIAGNOSTICS, CLASSIFICATIONS, AND DEVELOPMENT OF A REPORTING TEMPLATE FOR ACUTE DIVERTICULITIS OF THE COLON.....	279
41.	Normamatov Bakhriddin Pirmamatovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich OPTIMIZATION OF COMPREHENSIVE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ACUTE PURULENT CHOLANGITIS USING HYBRID MINIMALLY INVASIVE TECHNOLOGIES.....	293
42.	Nurillayev Khasan Zhamshidovich ACUTE CHOLECYSTITIS IN THE ELDERLY: FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL COURSE, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT.....	300
43.	Obidov Shokhrukh Khabibovich, Mamarajabov Sobirjon Ergashevich MODERN APPROACHES TO SURGICAL TREATMENT OF INGUINAL HERNIAS IN OBESE PATIENTS.....	306
44.	Rabbimova Maftuna Ulugbekovna. ENDOSCOPIC ULTRASOUND ELASTOGRAPHY: CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENTAL DIRECTIONS.....	313
45.	Rakhmatov Istodjon Samedjonovich THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF X-RAY EXAMINATIONS IN MEDICINE.....	337
46.	Ruziboyev Sanjar Abdusalomovich, Allaberdiyev Nemat Abdushukurovich, Shavazi Ramiz Nuralievich REMOTE RESULTS OF THE IMPROVED LIXTENSHTEIN MODIFICATION.....	343
47.	Ruziboev Sanjar Abdusalomovich, Mardonov Vohid Narzullayevich, Shavazi Ramiz Nuralievich EXPERIMENT OF APPLYING ANTI-ADHESIVE PREPARATIONS IN THE EXPERIMENT.....	352

48.	Rizayev Jasur Alimjanovich, Abdullayev Sayfulla Abdullayevich THE SIGNIFICANCE OF NUTRITIONAL SUPPORT IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PURULENT-NECROTIC INFLAMMATION OF SOFT TISSUES.....	360
49.	Rizayev Ezoz Alimdjanovich, Kurbaniyazov Zafarjon Babajanovich PREDICTION OF ACUTE PANCREATITIS OUTCOMES BASED ON LAPAROSCOPY DATA AND THE BALTHAZAR SCALE.....	365
50.	Ravshanov Mukhammadali Ikhtiyorovich, Askarov Pulat Azadovich MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF OBSTRUCTIVE JAUNDICE OF BENIGN ORIGIN.....	373
51.	Rashidova Xurshida Abduvoxidovna POSSIBILITIES OF CLINICAL AND LABORATORY AND INSTRUMENTAL STUDIES IN NON – ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE.....	379
52.	Salimov Eshdavlat Eshmakhmatovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH THYROID NODULES.....	386
53.	Sayinaev Farrukh Karamatovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich ASPECTS OF LAPAROSCOPIC HERNIOPLASTY FOR VENTRAL HERNIAS.....	392
54.	Salokhiddinov Jurabek Saidakhmatovich TOPICAL ISSUES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF TOXIC FORMS OF GOITER...	397
55.	Suvonov Shokhruxh Shukhrat ugli CURRENT METHODS OF TREATMENT OF LARGE AND GIANT VENTRAL HERNIAS USING TENSION-FREE HERNIOPLASTY.....	403
56.	Shirov Bobur Furkatovich, Mardieva Gulshod Mamatmuradova EVALUATION OF THE DIAGNOSTIC EFFECTIVENESS OF THE BONE COVERAGE COEFFICIENT AND SIDE RATIO COEFFICIENT COMPARED TO THE GRAF METHOD.....	409
57.	Shomurodov Khabibullo Abdumalik ugli, Daminov Feruz Asadullaevich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich APPLICATION OF LAPAROSCOPY IN SURGICAL TREATMENT OF ACUTE DESTRUCTIVE CHOLECYSTITIS.....	419
58.	Turakulov Vali Norkulovich. MEASURES TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE (COPD).....	424
59.	Tagaev Abror Ilkhomovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH PURULENT PLEURISIS.....	430
60.	Toirov Abdukhomit Suvonovich, Musoev Sodiqjon Toirovich THE ROLE OF ENDOVENOUS LASER COAGULATION IN THE COMPLEX TREATMENT OF VARICOSE VEINS OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES.....	437
61.	Turdumatov Jamshed Anvarovich, Sobirova Nilufar RADIOLOGICAL SEMIOTICS OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE IN TYPE II DIABETES MELLITUS.....	442
62.	Tukhtayev Firdavs Mukhidinovich, Ergashev Arslonbek Shukhratjon ugli LAPAROSCOPIC TREATMENT OF CYSTIC KIDNEY NEOPLASMS: EFFICACY AND RESULTS.....	451
63.	Umedov Xushvaqt Alisherovich, THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF VIDEOLAPAROSCOPY IN CLOSED ABDOMINAL INJURIES.....	457
64.	Umedov Xushvaqt Alisherovich IMPROVEMENTS IN DIAGNOSTIC AND THERAPEUTIC CAPABILITIES OF VIDEOLAPAROSCOPY WITH CLOSED ABDOMINAL LESIONS.....	463

65. **Usarov Sherali Nasretidinovich**
ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH INGUINAL HERNIAS.....474
66. **Yanova Elvira Umarjonovna, Urokov Farrukh Ibodullaevich**
TYPES OF ANGIODYSPLASIA IN KIMMERLE ANOMALY BY MAGNETIC RESONANCE ANGIOGRAPHY.....479
67. **Yuldashev Parda Arzikulovich, Rakhmanov Kosim Erdanovich, Davlatov Salim Sulaymonovich**
OPTIMIZATION OF SURGICAL APPROACHES IN THE TREATMENT OF POSTOPERATIVE VENTRAL HERNIAS.....491
68. **Alisher Zayniyev Faridunovich**
A NEW PLASMAPHERESIS METHOD FOR PREOPERATIVE PREPARATION IN PATIENTS WITH THYROTOXICOSIS.....499
69. **Ablyazov Otabek Vakhobovich, Yakubov Golib Akbarovich, Ablyazov Abduvakhob Abdumadzhidovich, Madumarova Zarnigor Shukhratovna, Turgunov Shomakhmud Shorakhimovich**
IMAGING METHODS FOR CERVICAL SPINAL CANAL STENOSIS.....508
70. **Kurbaniyazov Bakhodir Zafarzhonovich, Ashurov Akmal Khusanovich**
TACTICAL AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF TRANSABDOMINAL LAPAROSCOPIC HERNIALLOPLASTY FOR INGUINAL HERNIAS.....512
71. **Kilichev Rashid Nematovich, Mamarajabov Sobirjon Ergashevich, Babakalanov Shuhrat Ibragimovich, Oltiyev Elyor Doniyorovich.**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HAL-RAR AND LHP SURGICAL APPROACHES IN THE TREATMENT OF HEMORRHOIDS.....520
72. **Ahmedov Gayrat Keldibayevich, Gulamov Olimjon Mirzakhitovich, Azizov Temur Alisher ugli, Toshkenboyev Firdavs Ramatillo Zoda, Khudaynazarov Utkir Rabbimovich.**
ANASTOMOSIS IN ESOPHAGULAR CANCER OPERATIONS.....526
73. **Teshayev Shuxrat Jumayevich, Jarilkasinova Gauzar Januzakovna.**
SOCIAL AND CLINICAL-BIOCHEMICAL FACTORS IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF GASTRITIS AND ULCER DISEASE: STUDYING SMOKING AND PROFESSIONAL DEPENDENCE.....531
74. **Khaibullina Zarina Ruslanovna, Babajanov Azam Khasanovich, Djuraeva Nigora Mukhsumovna, Abdukhalimova Khanum Valentinovna**
VON WILLEBRAND FACTOR DYNAMICS AFTER RELATED LIVER TRANSPLANTATION.....538
75. **Khaydarova Nargiza Akhtamzhon kizi**
ANALYSIS OF MORPHOFUNCTIONAL AND MORPHOMETRIC FEATURES OF THE THYROID GLAND IN 5-MONTH-OLD MONGREL RATS IN THE OBSERVATION GROUP.....549
76. **Mardiyeva Gulshod Mamatmuradovna, Abdullaeva Mukhiba Nigmatovna, Matyakupov Azim Rustemovich, Nurmamatova Ozoda Abdurasul kizi.**
ROENTGEN-PROTEINOLOGICAL RELATIONSHIPS IN THE DYNAMICS OF PNEUMONIA IN NEWBORNS, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE DEGREE OF THEIR MATURITY.....556
77. **Karabyev Djamshidkhan Shavkatovich, Shakhanov Shavkat Safarovich, Shakirov Bobur**
PREVENTION AND EFFECTIVENESS OF ARTHRITIS IN PATIENTS WITH BURNS USING LOW VIBRATION LASER BEAMS.....564
78. **Исмаилов Зоҳиджан, Мирджурев Элбек**
ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ ПЕРИФЕРИЧЕСКОЙ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ, ИХ ДИАГНОСТИКА, ВЫБОР ПРАВИЛЬНОЙ ТАКТИКИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ И ШИРОКОЕ ВНЕДРЕНИЕ РЕАБИЛИТАЦИОННОЙ РАБОТЫ ПОСЛЕ ПЕРЕНЕСЕННЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ...570
79. **Ismailov Zakhidjon, Mirdjuraev Elbek**
EXAMINATION OF CHILDREN WITH NEUROPATHY, TIMELY DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND REHABILITATION MEASURES AFTER ILLNESSES.....578

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

УДК 616.61+616.617]-007.271-089

ISHMURADOV Bakhron Tursunovich
PhD
Samarkand State Medical University

EFFICACY OF ENDOSCOPIC BALLOON DILATION IN TREATMENT OF ACQUIRED URETERAL STRICTURES

For citation: Ishmuradov Bakhron Tursunovich . Efficacy of endoscopic balloon dilation in treatment of acquired ureteral strictures // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2025, vol. 10, issue 2.

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15198922>

ABSTRACT

The article evaluates the effectiveness of endoscopic balloon dilation in the treatment of acquired ureteral and ureteropelvic junction (UPJ) strictures. In balloon dilation (BD) of acquired ureteral strictures, the overall effectiveness was 82%. 13 patients (18.1%) required repeated dilation and installation of a stent with a sliding clutch. BD has proven itself to be a technically simple and effective procedure, which in some cases can be an alternative to open surgical interventions.

Keywords: balloon dilation, ureteral strictures, endoscopy.

ИШМУРАДОВ Бахрон Турсунович
К.м.н.

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЭНДОСКОПИЧЕСКОЙ БАЛЛОННОЙ ДИЛАТАЦИИ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ПРИОБРЕТЕННЫХ СТРИКТУР МОЧЕТОЧНИКОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье оценивается эффективность использования эндоскопической баллонной дилатации в лечении приобретенных стриктур мочеточников и лоханочно-мочеточникового сегмента (ЛМС). При баллонной дилатации (БД) приобретенных стриктур мочеточников общая эффективность составила 82 %. 13 пациентам (18,1%) потребовалось проведение повторной дилатации и установки стента с подвижной муфтой. БД показала себя как технически несложная и эффективная процедура, которая в ряде случаев может быть альтернативой открытым оперативным вмешательствам.

Ключевые слова: баллонная дилатация, стриктуры мочеточников, эндоскопия.

ISHMURADOV Baxron Tursunovich
T.f.n.
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

SIYDIK NAYLARINING ORTTIRILGAN STRIKTURALARIDA ENDOSKOPIK BALLONLI DILYATATSIYANING SAMARADORLIGI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada siydik naylarining va siydik nayi-jom segmentining (SNJS) orttirilgan strikturalarini davolashda endoskopik ballonli dilyatatsiyaning samaradorligi baholandi. Siydik naylarining orttirilgan strikturalarini ballonli dilyatatsiyaning (BD) umumiy samaradorligi 82% ni tashkil etdi. 13 (18,1%) nafar bemorlarda takroriy dilyatatsiya o'tkazilishi va harakatchan muftali stent o'rnatilishi talab etilgan. BD texnik jihatdan bajarilishi oson va samarali muolaja ekanligi, va ba'zi hollarda ochiq jarrohlik aralashuvlarga muqobil bo'lishi mumkinligi ko'rsatildi.

Kalit so'zlar: ballonli dilyatatsiya, siydik naylarining strikturalari, endoskopiya.

Introduction. Acquired ureteral strictures are usually of traumatic, postoperative, tuberculous, radiation or inflammatory origin. Postoperative ureteral strictures are quite common, their occurrence is associated with adhesive-sclerotic changes in the ureter and the surrounding tissues. Ureteral strictures can be single or multiple. Tuberculous strictures are usually multiple and form in areas of infiltrates and ulcers, post-radiation strictures develop more often in the lower third of the ureter after radiation therapy for malignant tumors of the genitals, rectum, and bladder. Post-radiation strictures are extended. Strictures developing after urological operations on the ureter can be localized in any section of the ureter and have different lengths [3,5].

Currently, various methods of reconstructive plastic surgery, replacement of the ureter with a fragment of the ileum, appendix, etc. are applied to restore the lumen of ureteropelvic junction (UPJ) and the ureter. These operations basically involve mandatory resection of the narrowed section of the ureter.

Endoscopic operations are widely used for strictures of any etiology and any localization and have the highest percentage of positive results in short (up to 1 cm) stenosis of post-inflammatory and traumatic etiology. According to various authors, the success of transurethral bougienage reaches 40-70%, balloon dilation 50-80% [1,2,3,4], however, reports on the effectiveness of endoscopic dilation of ureteral strictures and UPJ are contradictory [2].

Purpose. Evaluation of the effectiveness of endoscopic balloon dilation of acquired ureteral strictures and strictures of UPJ.

Material and methods. In the period 2016-2024, 72 balloon dilations (BD) of ureteral strictures and strictures of UPJ were performed at the Institute of Urology of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine together with the Department of Urology of the Samarkand State Medical University. Among all patients:

38 (52.8%) patients with postoperative ureteral strictures (upper third – 12 (31.6%), lower third – 16 (42.1%), UPJ – 10 (26.3%);

11 (15.3%) patients with strictures of the lower third of the ureters after radiation therapy;

6 (8.3%) patients with bilateral strictures and ureterohydronephrosis (UGN);

9 (12.5%) patients with strictures after ureterolithoextraction,

6 (8.3%) patients after extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy (ESWL) and

2 (2.8%) patients with postoperative ureteral strictures of a single kidney.

Of the 72 patients, 13 (18.1%) had undergone repeated BD due to recurrent strictures over the course of 1 year.

After studying the functional state of the kidney, establishing the localization and extent of the stricture, catheterization of the ureter was performed using an angiographic guide, a fluoroplastic or X-ray-positive standard catheter. The possibility of passing the guide through the narrowed section of the ureter and the level of the overcome obstacle in centimeters (according to the catheter marks) were determined.

Dilation of the stricture was performed with two types of dilation balloons: Microvasive 6-12 atm, with a balloon length of 4-10 cm, a balloon diameter of 27-30 Fr, or Balloon Dilation Catheter euca PW 10.0 x 6.0 - 115 Germany. After installing the balloon dilator, its balloon was filled with an X-ray contrast substance using a special device with a manometer to monitor the pressure in the

dilator. The initial pressure of 2-4 atm, at which stricture dilation is possible, upon reaching these values, the set pressure in the balloon is fixed by closing the tap for 3-5 minutes. In case of non-complete efficiency or inefficiency of stricture dilation, the pressure in the balloon is gradually increased (according to the technical characteristics of the balloon dilator) to 12 atm. As the balloon is filled with contrast agent, a "waist" appears on its surface - a filling defect, which represents the ureteral stricture. As the pressure in the balloon increases, the waist decreases in length and width. The disappearance of the waist and complete straightening of the balloon dilator walls along the entire length indicates that complete dilation of the narrowed section of the ureter or UPJ has been achieved. Dilation sessions are performed up to 3 times, with an exposure of 3-5 minutes. An internal stent of 8-10 Fr is installed along the guidewire for the purpose of adequate drainage of the kidney and formation of a ureter of a new diameter at the site of the stricture for a period of 6-8 weeks.

To form a sufficient lumen of the UPJ or ureter in patients with recurrent strictures, internal stents of 6-8 Fr with a sliding clutch of 14-16 Fr are used. Dilation was performed according to the specified technique, but a stent with a sliding clutch, previously fixed on the stent in the projection of the stricture, is installed at the level of the recurrent stricture (the level of the stricture is determined by catheterization and X-ray examination). Nephrostomies, if any, are removed 2-3 days after ureteral stenting. Stents are removed 6-8 weeks after the operation, when the patient is re-hospitalized.

Results. Dilation of ureteral strictures was performed in a retrograde and antegrade manner. In the presence of a postoperative nephrostomy or an imposed percutaneous nephrostomy, antegrade BD of the ureteral stricture is possible. Retrograde BD was performed in 58 (80,6%) patients, antegrade BD - in 14 (19,4%) patients. A follow-up examination in the remote period, from 6 months to 5 years, was conducted for all 72 patients. The result was assessed on the basis of a comprehensive examination, including ultrasound, survey and excretory urography, radioisotope renography, Doppler examination of the renal vascular system, the clinical condition of the patient and general clinical laboratory data.

A result was considered positive if there were no clinical symptoms of obstruction, no improvement or no deterioration in the functional state of the kidney, and no pronounced symptoms of pyelonephritis. In 13 patients, a recurrence of stricture was detected within a year: 5 at the level of UPJ and 8 at different levels of the ureter, of which 5 patients were after radiation therapy.

Recurrent ureteral and URC strictures in 13 (18.1%) patients were subjected to repeated dilation and installation of a stent with a sliding clutch during outpatient treatment and follow-up observation for 1-2 years. Further observation for 5 years had the following results: 3 patients developed a recurrent stricture with complete loss of renal function and its shrinkage. These patients underwent nephrectomy. 7 patients developed a recurrence of urolithiasis, exacerbation of chronic pyelonephritis against the background of impaired UPJ passability - surgical treatment was performed. In 3 patients with post-radiation strictures of the lower third of the ureters, repeated dilation sessions with stent installation were performed due to pronounced sclerotic changes in the retroperitoneal space and pelvis, one of them was transferred to chronic stent replacements on both sides every 3-4 months.

Discussion. In the course of treatment and observation of patients with acquired ureteral and UPJ strictures, we have established that the success of endoscopic technique depends on the length, severity of the stricture, development of complications in the postoperative period in the form of hematomas, urohematomas, sclerosis of the retroperitoneal space and the period of stricture formation. Thus, in patients with a stricture that has formed and exists for no more than 6 months, in 95% of cases it is possible to achieve complete dilation of the stricture, with older strictures, complete dilation is possible only in 75% of cases.

Conclusions. Retrograde and antegrade BD of acquired ureteral strictures and UPJ strictures is an effective method of treating ureteral strictures, allowing a number of patients to be spared repeated, traumatic, reconstructive and plastic surgeries (59 patients - 82%).

REFERENCES| ЧОҶКИ | IQTIBOSLAR:

1. Bachar GN, Mor E., Bartal G. Percutaneous balloon dilatation for the treatment of early and late ureteral strictures after renal transplantation: long - term follow - up. *Cardiovasc. Intervent. Radiol.* 2004 Jul - Aug. Vol. 27(4). P.335 - 8.
2. Lubennikov A.E., Trushkin R.N., Podkorytova O.L. The role of minimally invasive methods in the treatment of urological complications and diseases after kidney transplantation in the late period. *Nephrology and Dialysis.* Vol. 16, 2014; 426-438 (in Russ).
3. Minin A.E., Kagantsov I.M., Turabov I.A. Treatment of hydronephrosis – from nephrectomy to NOTES technologies. *Experimental and Clinical Urology.* 2013; 2:128-136 (in Russ).
4. Zorkin S.N., Gubarev V.I., Salnikov V.Yu., et al. High-pressure endoscopic balloon dilation as a method for treating ureteropelvic junction obstruction in children. *Urology Bulletin* 2017; 5(2): 5-11(in Russ).
5. Zuban O.N., Skornyakov S.N., Borodin E.P. et al. Endoscopic methods for correction of ureteral strictures. *Urology* 2013; 3:57-60 (in Russ).

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

10 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 10, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 10, ISSUE 2

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000